

Development of 3D Bioactive Silicate Based Glass-Ceramic Scaffolds with Hierarchical Porosity by Additive Manufacturing

Arish Dasan^a, Hamada Elsayed^{b,c}, Jozef Kraxner^a, Dusan Galusek^d, Enrico Bernardo^{*c}

^aDepartment of Glass Processing, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail:arish.dasan@tnuni.sk)

^bCeramics Department, National Research Centre, Cairo, Egypt

^cDepartment of Industrial Engineering, Università degli Studi di Padova, Padova, Italy

^dJoint glass centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChFT STU, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Due to their excellent bioactivity and biocompatibility, silicate based biomaterials have received much attention in bone tissue engineering. Bone Implants for bone regeneration ideally need highly porous scaffolds, pore interconnectivity, optimized mechanical strengths and adaptable manufacturing. While it is challenging to produce complex porous ceramic components via conventional shaping methods, additive manufacturing enables to fabricate such components.

Silicones are a class of preceramic polymers, also known as polymer derived ceramics (PDCs), which can yield SiO_2 upon thermal treatment in air. Mixing silicones with active fillers leads to silicate based, bioactive, polymer derived glass-ceramics. For example, well known bioactive akermanite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{MgSi}_2\text{O}_7$) ceramic foams were developed from a liquid silicone mixed with CaO and MgO precursors by firing at 1100 °C. Intensive foaming was caused by water evaporation due to the decomposition of the fillers $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and hydrated borax as extra filler (which also formed liquid phase upon firing; led nearly phase pure components) at ca. 300-350 °C before firing at 1100 °C. It should be noted that the obtained akermanite ceramics by PDCs route did not compromise its biological responses. The advantage of PDCs route is not limited to shaping possibilities ((porous scaffolds could be shaped with silicone polymers before ceramization occurs); but also desirable ceramics could be obtained relatively low temperature than conventional methods. In addition, the low cost, easy handling and commercially available raw materials are also advantages. This characteristic property has recently provoked the use of preceramic polymers with reactive fillers in additive manufacturing technologies.

Direct ink writing (DIW) is an additive manufacturing technique that can be used to form green bodies via layer-by-layer extrusion of viscous pastes. Generally, in order to produce ceramic pastes, it needs sacrificial organic binder (during heat treatment binder will completely burn out), while silicone polymers can act as nonsacrificial binder as it yield one of the reactant upon heat treatment, to produce ceramic phases of a targeted composition when mixed with fillers.

The research here presented was essentially aimed at producing reticulated akermanite scaffolds, by direct ink writing of a paste consisting of silicone resins with CaO and MgO precursors, and with the additional constraint of forming porous struts, that would favour the impregnation with body fluids and cell adhesion. Despite scaffolds exhibited numerous cracks, due to the gas release from silicone resin and CaCO_3 upon heating, crack-free scaffolds with dense and regular struts were achieved by using addition of small amount (1.5 wt%) of anhydrous sodium borate ($\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$). On the contrary, scaffolds with homogenous 'spongy' struts were obtained by using hydrated sodium borate. No cracks were observed even in the latter case, owing to water vapour release at low temperature, before ceramic conversion. Both type of scaffolds (with dense or porous struts) exhibited remarkable (compressive strength of 7.3 ± 1.1 MPa and 4.1 ± 0.3 MPa with porosity $56.6 \pm 2.6\%$ and $68.7 \pm 0.8\%$, respectively) strength-to-density ratios.

Keywords: Polymer derived glass ceramics; preceramic polymers; additive manufacturing; akermanite; direct ink writing; scaffolds.

References:

- [1] Bernardo E, Carlotti JF, Dias PM, Fiocco L, Colombo P, Treccani L, Hess U and Rezwan K, Novel akermanite-based Bioceramics from preceramic polymers and oxide fillers. *Ceram Int.* 2014;40:1029–1035.
- [2] Fiocco L, Li S, Stevens MM, Bernardo E, Jones JR, Biocompatibility and bioactivity of porous polymer-derived Ca-Mg silicate ceramics. *Acta Biomater.* 2017;50:56–67.
- [3] Fiocco L, Elsayed H, Daguano JKMF, Soares VO, Bernardo E, Silicone resins mixed with active oxide fillers and Ca–Mg Silicate glass as alternative/integrative precursors for wollastonite–diopside glass-ceramic foams. *J. Non-Cryst. Solids.* 2015;416:44-49.

Acknowledgment:

This paper is a part of the dissemination activities of project FunGlass. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.